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Framing an Environment and Sustainability Lens on Vocational Education and Training (VET): A Laminated System Analysis

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Abstract

With evidence of global climate change and ongoing ecological degradation, there is an urgent need to give more attention to sustainability within VET. This will ensure that VET does not remain complicit in reproducing the unjust and unsustainable trajectories of current economic and development pathways. While some progress has been made in policy and practice related to the ‘greening’ of VET, our analysis shows that much of the current response within VET to the environmental challenge reflects a minimalist reformist approach, characterised by ‘bolt-ons’ (Sterling, 2004) to existing institutional structures and curricula. This leaves the fundamental beliefs in productivism, industrialisation and growth in place, which, as argued by researchers working on green economy (e.g. Death, 2014), are oftentimes complicit in co-creation of the environmental crisis. As this has become obvious, new discourses to guide VET in response to the environmental crisis are emerging, with the most prominent being ‘just transitions’. In this paper, we consider the meaning(s) of these shifts in policy discourse in relation to evidence of movement in the VET system towards green economy and just transitions more broadly, for these movements cannot emerge without adequate attention to skills development, including in the VET system. We argue that the shift towards global sustainability, the greening of work, and the emergence of just transitions towards sustainability have implications for framing new approaches to learning vocationally.

Keywords

vocational education and training (VET), sustainability, UNESCO, just transitions, sustainability transitions, green economy.

1 Orientation and methodology

To offer grounded case examples of these trends in order to iteratively consider their implication. We draw on examples of VET policy and practice from Africa and from South

Africa in particular, as this is where most of our empirical work is grounded. In noting this, however, we emphasise here that our account is not primarily empirical, rather it is meta-reflective offering a ‘landscape view’ of the field as it is emerging.

We begin by offering an immanent critique of the state of VET discourse, policy and practice from the vantage point of VET and sustainability. This is followed by a deliberation on the shifts in political economy discourse as it shifts via encounters with ecological dynamics and debates around green economy, just transitioning and sustainability more broadly. We then consider how these discourses are also related to educational thinking, with a view to developing a mechanism for reviewing the greening of VET over time. While the paper overall is not an empirical paper, to develop insight into some of the shifts in the greening of VET we draw on data that is drawn primarily from two projects carried out with others for UNESCO and the ILO in which VET policies from across Africa were reviewed and stakeholders interviewed and/or surveyed. Beyond this, we also draw on insights from two recent major research projects in which we were all involved (one on South Africa; the other on South Africa and Uganda). Our analysis shows that VET is being shaped by an emerging political-economy-ecology lens that ultimately requires a whole systems approach to understanding the sustainability transition within VET if it is to be meaningfully embraced with a commitment to radical transformation and social and ecological justice. We offer this as a contribution to the VET literature, which, overall, has been slow to engage with the question of what skills are needed (and how will they be developed) for sustainable futures.

2 A brief immanent critique of VET: Why a shift is needed to embrace sustainability

The beginning of industrialisation in Europe is crucial to how we understand VET. In transitioning to a more industrialised economy, the previous vocational learning approaches were transformed into ‘modern’ forms, often linked to public vocational providers (the archetypal VET institutions) through day or block release schemes, and sometimes grounded in tripartite agreements between state, employer and trade unions (e.g., Fuller and Unwin, 2009; Deissinger and Gonon, 2021). Whilst the Germanic and Anglophone traditions, for instance, are very different, they share a common core of preparing (predominantly male) youth for the world of work. This world of work was shaped by the wider process of industrialisation and had a particular focus on preparation for key industrial sectors such as mining, metals and motors. In the colonised south, the development of formal VET initially was heavily conditioned by the feasibility of large-scale colonisation. Formal VET programmes developed most rapidly where climate conditions allowed for large-scale white settlement, leading to a form of “settler VET” (McGrath and Russon, 2022). This saw growing local white populations receive training to replace imported white labour with indigenous populations excluded from access to certain trades and occupations. For instance, South Africa’s model of ‘racial Fordism’ (Gelb, 1991) led to massive investments in parastatal industries such as steel and railways, as well as the arrival of automobile production in 1923, with a concomitant growth in public VET (Badroodien, 2004; Gamble, 2021). Similar strong development of formal VET can be found in the Latin American experience of import substitution (Castro, 1998).

Elsewhere in the colonised territories, climate and disease mitigated against large-scale white settlement. Extractive industries here relied more on small numbers of white overseers and large amounts of indigenous labour, with little attempt made at formal skilling. In many such settings, many of which achieved independence in the second half of the twentieth century in Africa and South Asia in particular, there was typically initial dependence on expatriate skilled workers, followed by a growth in local skills development around extractive industries and some heavy industry.

In many places, North and South, formal vocational education remains tightly linked to the same old sectors, even though there may be few new jobs being created in them. Moreover, at

a discursive level, the heterodox VET literature remains largely located within earlier political economy thinking and has not yet engaged sufficiently with the political-economy-ecology move. Although it has addressed extractive effects on human labour, it has not extended this to nature and remains largely in a productivist bind (Anderson, 2008; McGrath, 2012). This approach is seen as having three problems. First of all, the understanding of the full purpose of VET has been improvised. Secondly, it avoids the issue of unsustainability. Lastly, it is based on an inaccurate account of actually existing labour markets, especially in the global South. This critique has not been seriously engaged in the mainstream VET literature. Indeed, even less radical accounts of sustainability are rare in the major VET journals. In the past 20 years, only eight articles have been published in the five leading VET journals that address sustainability issues (Coll et al., 2003; Sack, 2012; Brown, 2013; Brown et al., 2013; Draper et al., 2014; Evans and Stroud, 2016; Comyn, 2018; Pavlova, 2018; Liu et al., 2020). Most are small-scale empirical studies about attitudes, with very little engagement in theoretical debates regarding what is meant by ‘green’ or ‘sustainable’, let alone an engagement in political-economy-ecology arguments.

3 VET and an increasing focus on greening, sustainability and just transitions in economy and society

As the argument for a green and sustainable economic transition grows, more institutions have become involved in defining the VET agenda, including the UNEP and the ILO (see below), and increased pressure is being placed on the VET sector to orient programmes, relations, curricula and institutional cultures towards sustainability. This is, however, not an easy task, as there are often internal contradictions with other programmes in the VET institutions (e.g. supporting VET for the fossil fuel industries). Additionally, the fact that the green economy discourse is in itself complex and rapidly shifting, as are the issues that the environment and sustainability sector seek to respond to (e.g. climate change has shifted from a science to a policy to a technology to an ethical concern affecting all sectors of society).

Interrogating these shifts can help to frame the nature of sustainability response and can help VET educators and researchers to better frame their efforts towards supporting the greening of VET or VET work for climate action, circular economies and/or Just Transitions. The global impetus for VET and sustainable futures has been amplified by the proclamation of the Sustainable Development Goals in 2015.

While the emergence of sustainable development discourses heralded an important turn, it quickly became clear that sustainable development remains vague and imprecise, and is often critiqued for being a ‘floating signifier’ (Ferguson, 2015; Ramsarup, 2017), a concept that can be made to mean almost anything, in keeping with the discursive histories of the two component words. This “floating” continues when we come to look at green jobs and the green economy. These are concepts that are potentially crucial to VET as the educational sector preparing young people for the world of work.

Similarly, the green economy has largely been a descriptive and normative discourse used by policy analysts and often emerges as an empty signifier when agencies like CEDEFOP argue that “green skills are becoming a part of almost every job” (CEDEFOP 2019) or agencies state that ‘all jobs are green jobs’. The work of Death (2014), Faccar (2014) and Ferguson (2015) (cf Table 1 below) provide typologies of green economy discourses that can enable more critical engagement with these in VET research and practice, with the most radical of these being ‘green revolution’, ‘transformational’ or ‘strong’ green economy’ discourses that signal a deeper commitment to sustainable futures that move beyond sustaining the existing economic model of (neo-)liberal capitalism and its ecologically destructive / extractivist tendencies. Weaker forms of green economy are typically referred to as ‘green growth’, ‘green resilience’, or

‘incrementalist’, and signify reactionary, or even greenwashing approaches to sustainable futures.

Table 1

Typologies of the Green Economy

Four discourses of the Green Economy (Death 2014)	Discourses related to the Green Economy (Faccer et al. 2014)	Discourses related to the Green Economy (Ferguson, 2015)
<i>Green Revolution:</i> radical, revolutionary transformation on economic (and hence social and political) relationships to bring them in line with natural limits and ecological virtues.	<i>Transformative Discourse:</i> incorporates critical perspectives calling for a more radical review of society’s economic and broader developmental objectives.	<i>Strong Green Economy Discourses:</i> embody post growth or limits to growth as central to their macroeconomic trajectory and encompasses measures of welfare as a critical indicator.
<i>Green Transformation:</i> explicit focus on social justice, equity and redistribution (including intergenerationally) where economic growth is a means rather than an end.	<i>Reformist Discourse:</i> diverse agendas for a green economy, with an emphasis on the right combination of actions and long-term planning to achieve environmental benefits as well as stronger economic growth.	
<i>Green Growth:</i> green markets provide economic opportunities representing a recasting of the relationship between environment and economics with an emphasis on new markets, new services and new forms of consumption.	<i>Incrementalist Discourse:</i> defined by a broad acceptance of the prevailing macro-economic paradigm and a focus on greater use of market-based tools to drive a green economy transition.	<i>Transformational Green Economy Discourses:</i> reflect elements of selective growth often encompassing green consumerism and modified GDP as an indicator. However, both these categories still utilise GDP as a signifier of socio-economic development.
<i>Green Resilience:</i> essentially reactionary and cautious with an emphasis on environmental scarcity, climate change and resource depletion and the need to implement technological solutions to build local self-sufficiency / resilience.		<i>Weak green economy discourses:</i> have a macroeconomic trajectory of green growth and encompass unmodified GDP as an indicator.

Death’s typology is based on and focuses on national strategies from the Global South, with his overall argument making a strong call for the model of economic growth to be transformed in ways that involve explicit political interventions geared to transforming the structure of the economy. Faccer et al. present three emerging agendas around the green economy. We have also focused on Ferguson’s typology, as we believe that it represents an evolution of the ‘weak/strong’ dichotomy from sustainability’ definitions, thus providing a useful basis for a framework of green economy visions. A significant rearticulatory move in Ferguson’s argument is to attach notions of well-being to economic security than economic growth. His

argument enables a continuum so that “transformative articulations of green economy provide the basis for a shift from the currently dominant weak green economy to a future strong green economy” (Ferguson 2015, p. 27).

A prevailing critique of general green economy discourses are that they are too closely aligned to current systems. It is suggested that they do not consider potential limits to growth. Moreover, they are characterised as oversimplified and overoptimistic. All concepts relating to the green economy place the economic sphere at the centre of any debate on future viability. According to this view, we can only save the planet with the economy, not against it. From these descriptions of transformative greening discourses, we can see that an inclusive green economy is much more than an economic growth agenda which sees new prospects for economic activity using natural resources, thus representing new forms of green capitalism or ecological modernisation. Rather, it raises significant challenges to the idea that environmental issues can be resolved within the current political economic system without fundamental social, economic and political change, hence differentiating meanings within green economy discourses is important. Also, it is equally important not lose a focus on the intentionality, which is to reframe current systems towards sustainable futures.

4 VET Analysis from a sustainability perspective

While there has been emphasis on green skills for VET as can be seen from the above discussion, there is limited work that considers the emerging trends in greening of VET critically to the demand for sustainable futures. The Environment and Sustainability Education (ESE) literature shows more evidence of engagement with especially more radical, transformational implications for education and skills development than the VET literature. This literature does a better job of thinking about educational providers and sustainability more systematically and transformatively, so we will briefly consider the work of Sterling (2004) as it offers a good analytical tool for analysing the greening of VET programmes and policy from an education and training sector perspective. He suggests that there are four predominant types of sustainability responses (that resonate with the typologies in Table 1 above) that are useful for considering implications for education system change.

Table 2

Comparing social and educational responses to sustainability (Sterling, 2004)

Sustainability transition	Response	State of sustainability	State of education
1. Very weak	Denial, rejection or minimum	No change (or token)	No change (or token)
2. Weak	‘Bolt-on’	Cosmetic reform	Education about sustainability
3. Strong	‘Build-in’	Serious greening	Education for sustainability
4. Very Strong	Rebuild or redesign	Wholly integrative	Sustainable education

The relationship between these and the three sets of green discourses above is apparent in the evolution or development of green skills discourses in VET guiding documents and practices over time, a period of twenty / thirty years, as also briefly introduced above. In the next section we will review these trends drawing on the Sterling framework. As can be seen above, definitions of green economy and the means of moving towards sustainability are contested.

However the definitions are useful to consider, as they typically involve recalibrating an introduction of new ways of thinking. In institutional terms, this is about a new logic being applied to economic and social policies, practices and systems in order to support economy, ecology and equity. In the sections below we examine how these have been applied and/or are developing within VET systems in Africa. To do this we draw on data from our studies and work on VET in Africa. As indicated above, this offers an iterative tool for reviewing the emerging VET greening practices.

5 Analysis 1: Predominance of ‘bolt-on’ or more cosmetic reforms

As noted above, there have been various efforts to influence the greening of VET. These efforts have been mainly led by UNESCO-UNEVOC teams and centres. A key focus of this work has mainly been to influence the greening of VET policies. At the policy level, there has been a response from the supply side through UNESCO’s lead role in international VET policy development.

What is evident are embryonic policy interventions to bring ‘green aspects’ into some parts of the TVET system, which lead to various ‘bolt-on’ initiatives in the service of specific sectors, for example:

The aim to “introduce climate change into the curricula at all levels”, in the TVET sector, is an explicitly stated intervention of Lesotho’s NSDP II (GoL, 2018, p.111). Lesotho National Strategic Development Plan II (NSDP II) identified tourism as one of the productive sectors with great potential to create jobs and contribute significantly towards poverty reduction. The country aims to diversify tourism products by, among other things, promoting “Sustainable ecotourism” (GoL, 2018, p. 97). The intention is to mainstream ecotourism in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET), which will expand job creation and sustainability.

As noted above, policy movement has only really just started, with ‘bolt-on’ interventions as the end results. Substantive greening of vocational providers is yet to emerge, and as yet this has not been discussed much in the wider academic literature. Subsequently, reports on greening of TVET providers has mainly been confined to the grey literature of the development community.

Where public, formal VET providers are seeking to engage with the challenge, their approaches typically focus on first two pillars, and even when efforts are made, they are plagued by interrelated challenges as expressed in this Kenyan study by Jubungei (2020, p. 32):

Despite the importance of green skills in nurturing green economy that supports green growth, evidence from Kenya shows gaps in TVET institutions’ ability to develop green skills. Jahonga et al., (2015) for instance, point out that lack of human resources and requisite skills are among the major challenges to green technology and that the TVET courses on offer do not integrate green technology. Were and Ferej (2018) argue that insufficient integrated sustainable content in TVET training and lack of technical skills specific for transition to green economy were impediments to greening TVET. Murgor (2017) avers that TVET training fails to inculcate green skills (soft skills) relevant for survival in self-employment.

In Sterling’s terms, this amounts to a ‘bolt-on’ of sustainability ideas to the existing system, while the system itself remains largely unchanged, and efforts are impeded as described by Jubungei (2020) where they are arising. This results in largely an adaptive, first order change or learning. While this is necessary as a key starting point for changes towards sustainability, through this response, the dominant paradigm and the institutional /system maintains its original stability despite key efforts to the contrary.

Since vocational education is closely linked to the world of work, it is important to consider both educational and occupational systems as TVET learning pathways are constituted by both educational and occupational progression (Ramsarup, 2017). Most countries reported that they did have an occupational classification system, and the judgements from the respondents were fairly responsive to greening imperatives. However the specifics on what mid level and / or new green occupations have emerged were unclear. The survey also showed that most entry points in terms of represented occupations are at professional levels, mostly requiring postgraduate qualifications. Greater representation of entry level environmental occupations are to enable better access into the sector as technical skill levels needs to be explored, which will have implications for TVET pathways to enable better education and training opportunities. This point was also made by Ramsarup (2015) and Rosenberg et al, (2020). The focus on developing better understanding of greening of occupations is important for VET advancement for sustainable futures, as 53% of organisations surveyed indicated that they utilise occupational standards in design of TVET curricula.

It is imperative for TVET to be more pro- active in embracing provisioning and learning pathways for sustainable futures as this has implications for teaching and learning. This is also a complex issue as curriculum for TVET tends to be centrally controlled, when the adaptive needs may be locally shaped. For example climate change adaptation strategies for agriculture may differ in different regions due to climatic conditions, ecotopes and more. In the survey, 67% of respondents indicated that TVET curricula for their qualifications are nationally prescribed and they follow these national curricula. This poses a constraint on responsiveness to local emerging issues. While this is the case, there are some curriculum innovations emerging to respond to the demands for greening occupations, and green economy development. For example,

- Mauritius has aimed to equip TVET trainees, in-service workers and technicians across various fields with green skills in order to enhance their employability. In achieving this aim, the TVET sector has created several new green qualifications and competencies (UNESCO 2014). These include a module on awareness of environmental issues in all TVET curricula; Training in the installation, maintenance and servicing of photovoltaic systems; Training in the installation and maintenance of solar water heaters; Training in the use of eco-friendly refrigerants; Training Module on environmental and sustainable development in the Diploma Of Hotel Management Course.
- In Lesotho, stargazing is being promoted as an important new stream of sustainability work focused around ‘astrotourism’, which focuses on travel to somewhat remote locations and on adventures that are unique in search for unpolluted views of the cosmos. The introduction of an ecotourism programme that entails astrotourism can greatly enhance the quality of TVET programmes in Lesotho. Prioritizing the mainstreaming of ecotourism within TVET offers important possibilities for local economic development and the sustainability spin offs, and would include reorienting of the current ‘development’ trajectory of indiscriminate lighting and air pollution; as well as to expand ecotourism-based job opportunities.
- In the Seychelles, agro-processing is a very important area which has led to a recently introduced Diploma in Sustainable Agriculture. Aquaculture was also identified as a new area that links the blue and green economies. The Seychelles Institute of Technology is offering programmes in rainwater harvesting and climate change, aimed at people who are self-employed. Additionally, developments are taking place in IT and greening.
- In South Africa, since 2013, the German Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development’s Programme Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) and Skills for Green Jobs (S4GJ) have, in cooperation with the South African DHET and DST, run a pilot project on the ‘Greening of TVET colleges.’ Amongst other projects, the collaborators developed specialised elective subjects in Renewable Energy

Technologies (RET) for the National Curriculum Vocational in Electrical Infrastructure Construction (NCV-EIC). Thus, a key area of TVET provision for the green economy are the RET subjects that are offered at introductory, intermediate and advanced levels. In this case, the curriculum intervention shaped the national qualification.

The discussion above indicates that there is emergence of greening of TVET taking place at policy, occupational system, and curriculum levels in the African countries involved in our studies. However, these are mostly following the ‘bolt-on’ interventionist approaches outlined by Stirling (2004) which mainly focus on education about sustainability in specific sectors. Few of these are systemically oriented towards wider transformation of the TVET system itself. While necessary, such interventions may not be sufficient if TVET is to become a strong sector contributing to sustainable futures. We turn now to a second analysis, where we examine some interventions that are leaning more towards the ‘build-in’ and ‘reframe’ approaches in Stirling’s framework that also reflect stronger and more radical commitments to sustainability.

6 Analysis 2: Towards transformational approaches

There are some encouraging developments that are pointing towards the conceptualisation and development of more transformational approaches to greening of TVET for sustainable futures. Key amongst these are UNESCO’s new strategy for TVET (UNESCO, 2022). There is a further evolution of UNESCO’s conceptualisation of greening TVET. As noted above, the strategy is now explicitly about “Transforming TVET for successful and just transitions”. Although the language of just transitions is not explored further in the short document, this represents a significant shift in language. The three strategic priorities are:

1. Skills for individuals to learn, work and live
2. Skills for economies to transition towards sustainable development
3. Skills for inclusive and resilient societies (UNESCO, 2022, p. 7).

The first of these reflects much of UNESCO’s VET policy concerns over recent decades in which employability, productivity and entrepreneurship are emphasized but within a UNESCO framing of inclusion, citizenship and lifelong learning. Noteworthy under this heading is a statement that “Training will need to be reoriented towards ... occupations that expand as all sectors shift towards environmentally sustainable production processes” (UNESCO, 2022, p. 7). The second, of course, is the most obvious “green priority”, framed here in terms of anticipation of skills needs caused by job destruction and creation in the context of just transitions. The third reflects the longstanding UNESCO concern with skills for inclusive societies but, strikingly, adds in the environmental framing of “resilient”. The draft strategy argues that: “Climate change and other facets of environmental degradation will increasingly represent a major threat to the stability and resilience of societies. TVET and skills development can play a part in alleviating these concerns” (UNESCO, 2022, p. 8).

All of this reflects the slow deepening of UNESCO’s green skills discourse over the past decade. However, our point regarding UNESCO’s policy work at the country level could serve as a reminder that global policy discourses may be only slowly reflected at the national level. Nonetheless, data from recent policy research in Africa suggests that the moment may be right for a move towards greener skills policies and practices.

7 Towards a political-economy-ecology account of VET

In recent work undertaken in a VET 4.0 Africa research collective, we have been involved in developing an approach to VET that gives more attention to sustainability within VET to enable a move away from the underpinning modes of productivist thinking that are implicit within it. We have done this via conceptualizing a political-economy-ecology approach that reviews how conventional VET is deeply embedded in the wider ‘Capitalocene’ (Moore, 2015) system. Outlining the limited, adaptive response from VET to sustainability, as also outlined above, we

offer some pointers on a way forward. Moreover, there is little sense that training for unending production and consumption is simply unsustainable (Anderson, 2008; McGrath, 2012).

As Anderson notes, VET:

uncritically mirrors the dominant logic of industrial society and produces its subjects as compliant and compulsive agents of economic growth, largely inured to the environmental consequences of their habitual behaviours. Located at the interface between education, the labour market and civil society, VET performs a crucial role in the constitution, population and legitimization of the vocations and professions, which are the main generators of economic growth.

Cast within the ethos of productivism and the ideological framework of neoliberalism, the institution of VPE [VET] is based on a restricted and instrumental view of lifeworlds which reduces people and the environment to the status of human and natural resources for economic exploitation. (Anderson, 2008, p. 106 and p. 121)

Anderson here is drawing in particular on Giddens (1994) but more recently there have been a series of accounts that bring out the environmental aspect of this critique even more strongly (but see also earlier work by Gorz, 1989). This literature highlights the complex interconnections of the political economy tradition (which is dominant in heterodox accounts of VET) and that of political ecology (e.g., Bond, 2002; Forsyth, 2003; di Munzio, 2015; Malm, 2016; Moore, 2016; Scoones, 2016; Satgar, 2018). For example, Malm's account of 'fossil capitalism' highlights the centrality of the relationship between carbon-centric development and capitalist accumulation. Much of the literature highlights the close relationship between controlling natural resources and controlling labour that was central to the emerging logic of industrialisation. This had a particular, highly racialised inflection in imperial settings and continues in postcolonial forms of extractivism. This political ecology literature seeks to offer "a social response to the oblivion of nature by political economy" (Leff, 2015, 33, cf. VET Africa 4.0 Collective, 2023).

VET needs to be understood as existing in a particular moment in time and space and as having a history that reflects the interplay of systems of learning and working, themselves grounded in wider cultural, economic, political and social arrangements. Expanding the conventional VET account outlined above in our immanent critique of VET, is a small and growing literature based on our earlier research (e.g., McGrath and Powell, 2016; Ramsarup, 2017; Rosenberg et al., 2020; McGrath and Russon, 2022; VET Africa 4.0 Collective, 2023) that is beginning to move towards a political-economy-ecology approach to VET.

This body of work, including McGrath (2020) and the VET 4.0 Africa Collective (2023) argues that taking the sustainability challenge seriously means disrupting conventional VET assumptions about skills for employability / productivity / growth. As an emergent body of heterodox literature, it suggests that VET research needs to begin addressing questions of how vocational learning can "promote decent work that contributes both to sustainable livelihoods, individuals and communities, and to wider efforts to restructure work and economic activities so that we live within our planetary boundaries" (McGrath, 2020, 8).

There is a directionality of the Just Transition which seeks to ensure distributive, reparative and justice in and through VET, this indicates that we need a more radical/disruptive whole system approach rather than the fragmented approach that is currently evident. We conclude this review with some suggestions on how we can move to a more proactive, transformative praxis oriented system and what the implications of this will be for the underpinning institutional, social and economic conditions that enable/constrain VET. In other words, we offer ways forward to move beyond the 'bolt-on' approach to sustainability in VET, instead seeking out more 'wholly integrative' approaches as in Stirling's (2004) framework above.

Seen in this light, sustainability is not just another issue to be added to an overcrowded curriculum, but a gateway to a different view of curriculum, pedagogy, organisational change, policy and particularly of ethos. As we have argued above, the effect of patterns of unsustainability on our current and future prospects is so pressing that the response of VET should not be predicated only on bolt-on approaches to ‘integration of sustainability’ into VET, because this invites a limited, adaptive, response. In our view, and based on our emerging body of research, we propose that a whole system approach to VET would involve a multi-levelled response including the following:

1) At macro levels - we would need to examine national policies /regulatory frameworks/industrial plans and the implications they would have for transitioning TVET - environmental.

2) At the sector level - examine global changes (e.g. water security, climate change etc.), innovation trends and industrial planning - and examine how sustainability oriented skills and occupational changes could be integrated and planned for as an integral part of this change.

3) Occupational levels of analysis of occupational change and skills, at one level this will mean understanding the lock-ins in the value chain (e.g. the predominance of monoculture agriculture) and how they can be overcome in relation to local realities (e.g. predominance of small scale farmers in Africa) and what implications this has for the changing nature of work.

4) On another level, this will mean understanding how occupations will and are changing. As we have argued above, a more nuanced idea of how the transition will impact occupations will assist in making more relevant educational decisions.

5) Training and Educational provisioning which will involve mapping qualifications, curriculum analysis in relation to sustainability transition needs; examining learning pathways, articulation opportunities, upscaling and re-educating training providers to embrace more systemic principles of education as sustainability (cf. Stirling, 2004), and curriculum innovations that cross boundaries and reframe education.

6) At a micro level, thinking about learning and work transitioning, transformative learning in VET contexts (e.g. Lotz-Sisitka & Pesanayi, 2020) and the how young people can move within streams of work (laterally and vertically).

7) Relationship between the levels - Coordination and planning between levels Central role of ministries in driving a whole system approach. It does not mean that one size fits all, it cannot be top down - need an understanding of a bottom up approach. This could be a Place based / disrupt form traditional notion of firm as central Relate to local possibilities for employment and livelihoods.

8) Beyond thinking about and inclusion of economic actors only - there is a need to consider other actors such as those involved in using VET for livelihoods construction, especially in contexts where informality is a key feature of the VET landscape.

References

- Anderson, D. (2008). Productivism, vocational and professional education, and the ecological question. *Vocations and Learning*, 1(2), 105-129.
- Avis, J. (2018). Socio-technical imaginary of the fourth industrial revolution and its implications for vocational education and training: A literature review. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 70(3), 337-363.
- Avis, J., & Avis, J. (2020). Conclusion: Vocational Education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution—Education and Employment in a Post-Work Age. *Vocational Education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution: Education and Employment in a Post-Work Age*, 103-116.
- Badroodien, A. (2004). Technical and vocational education provision in South Africa from 1920 to 1970.

- Bond, P. (2002). *Unsustainable South Africa*. Pietermaritzburg: University of KwaZulu Natal Press.
- Brown, M. (2013). The development of green skills through the local TAFE Institute as a potential pathway to regional development. *International Journal of Training Research*, 11(1), 27-43.
- Brown, M., Sack, F., & Piper Rodd, C. (2013). Student voice in 'skills for sustainability': A missing component from the demand side of Australian Vocational Education and Training. *International Journal of Training Research*, 11(3), 213–224. <https://doi.org/10.5172/ijtr.2013.11.3.213>
- Castro, C. D. M. (1998). The Stubborn Trainers vs. The Neoliberal Economists: Will Training Survive the Battle?
- Coll, R. K., Taylor, N., & Nathan, S. (2003). Using work-based learning to develop education for sustainability: a proposal. *Journal of Vocational education and Training*, 55(2), 169-182.
- Comyn, P. J. (2018). Skills, employability and lifelong learning in the Sustainable Development Goals and the 2030 labour market. *International Journal of Training Research*, 16(3), 200-217.
- Deissinger, T., & Gonon, P. (2021). The development and cultural foundations of dual apprenticeships—a comparison of Germany and Switzerland. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 73(2), 197-216.
- Di Munzio, T. (2015). *Carbon Capitalism*. Rowan and Littlefield International, London.
- Draper, F., Oltean-Dumbrava, C., Kara-Zaitri, C., & Newbury, B. (2014). Individual learning on environmental vocational education and training courses does not always lead to the workplace application of knowledge and skills. *Journal of Education and Work*, 27(6), 651-677.
- Evans, C., & Stroud, D. (2016). Greening steel work: Varieties of Capitalism and the 'greening' of skills. *Journal of Education and Work*, 29(3), 263-283.
- Faccar, K., Nahman, A., & Audouin, M. (2014). Interpreting the green economy: Emerging discourses and their considerations for the Global South. *Development Southern Africa*, 31(5), 642-657.
- Ferguson, P. (2015). The green economy agenda: business as usual or transformational discourse?. *Environmental Politics*, 24(1), 17-37.
- Forsyth, T. (2003). *Critical Political Ecology*. London: Routledge.
- Fuller, A., & Unwin, L. (2009). Change and continuity in apprenticeship: The resilience of a model of learning. *Journal of education and work*, 22(5), 405-416.
- Gamble, J. (2021). The legacy imprint of apprenticeship trajectories under conditions of segregation and Apartheid in South Africa. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 73(2), 258-277.
- Gelb, S. (Ed.). (1991). *South Africa's economic crisis*. New Africa Books.
- Giddens, A. (1994). *Beyond Right and Left*. Polity, Cambridge.
- Gorz, A. (1989). *Critique of Economic Reason*. London: Verso.
- Jebungei, K. N. (2020). Green skills and sustainable economy in Kenya: The influence of TVET trainer competencies. *Africa Journal of Technical and Vocational Education and Training*, 5(1), 29-40.
- Leff, E. (2015). Political ecology: a Latin American perspective. *Desenvolvimento e meio ambiente*, 35(35), 29-64.
- Liu, X., Chen, Y., Yang, Y., Liu, B., Ma, C., Craig, G. R., & Gao, F. (2022). Understanding vocational accounting students' attitudes towards sustainable development. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 74(2), 249-269.

- Majumdar, S. (2010, November). Greening TVET: Connecting the dots in TVET for sustainable development. In *16th IVETA-CPSC International Conference on "Education for Sustainable Development in TVET"* Manila, Philippines.
- Malm, A. (2016). *Fossil capital: The rise of steam power and the roots of global warming*. Verso Books.
- McGrath, S. (2012). Vocational education and training for development: A policy in need of a theory?. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 32(5), 623-631.
- McGrath, S. (2020). *Skilling for sustainable futures*. TEF Background Paper Series, University of Bristol. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4022328>
- McGrath, S., & Powell, L. (2016). Skills for sustainable development: Transforming vocational education and training beyond 2015. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 50, 12-19.
- McGrath, S., & Russon, J. A. (2022). Towards sustainable vocational education and training: thinking beyond the formal. *Southern African Journal of Environmental Education*, 38.
- Moore, J. W. (Ed.). (2016). *Anthropocene or capitalocene?: Nature, history, and the crisis of capitalism*. Pm Press.
- Pavlova, M. (2018). Fostering inclusive, sustainable economic growth and "green" skills development in learning cities through partnerships. *International Review of Education*, 64, 339-354.
- Ramsarup, P. (2017). A critical realist dialectical understanding of learning pathways associated with two scarce skill environmental occupations within a transitioning systems frame. *Unpublished PhD thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa*.
- Rosenberg, A. (2020). No jobs on a dead planet: the international trade union movement and just transition. *Just Transitions. Social Justice in the Shift Towards a Low-Carbon World*, 32-55.
- Rosenberg, E., Ramsarup, P., & Lotz-Sisitka, H. (2020). *Green Skills Research in South Africa: Models, Cases and Methods*. Routledge.
- Sack, F. (2012). Gen Green: Changes in Australian apprentices' and trainees' experience of skills and sustainability from 2008 to 2011. *International Journal of Training Research*, 10(1), 30-42.
- Satgar, V. (2018). *The climate crisis: South African and global democratic eco-socialist alternatives* (p. 372). Wits University Press.
- Scoones, I. (2016). The politics of sustainability and development. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 41:263–319.
- Sterling, S. (2004). Higher education, sustainability, and the role of systemic learning. *Higher education and the challenge of sustainability: Problematics, promise, and practice*, 49-70.
- UNESCO, (2012). Shanghai consensus: recommendations of the Third International Congress on Technical and Vocational Education and Training, <https://unevoc.unesco.org/home/UNESCO+Publications/lang=en/akt=detail/qs=5457>.
- UNESCO. (2016). *UNESCO Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) (2016-2021)*. UNESCO, Paris.
- UNESCO. (2022). *UNESCO Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) (2022-2027)*. UNESCO, Paris.
- UNESCO-UNEVOC 2014 "International Framework for Action: Greening TVET" (Draft).
- UNESCO-UNEVOC. (2012). Greening TVET for Sustainable Development. Report of the UNESCO-UNEVOC online Conference. 22 October to 2 November. https://unevoc.unesco.org/fileadmin/user_upload/docs/e-Forum_Synthesis_report_Greening_TVET.pdf.

VET Africa 4.0 Collective (2023). *Transitioning Vocational Education in Africa*. Bristol University Press, Bristol, forthcoming.

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